

CODATA Kenya: Statement on Joining CODATA

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Kenya is doing everything to enhance its ability to operate in the digital environment that requires preservation and sharing of information in order to empower citizens through access to information resources. As Kenya endeavors to do this, it is faced with challenges. The following ten challenges are the most significant:

- 1) Lack of policy on Open Data Management: for instance, publicly-funded and generated data is not structured in a way that enables the data to be fully discoverable and usable by end users
- 2) Lack of digital data-preservation policy and data standards
- 3) There is need to build information systems that support interoperability and information accessibility
- 4) There is need to strengthen data management and release practices
- 5) There is need to create and maintain a public data listing
- 6) There is need to strengthen measures to ensure that privacy and confidentiality are fully protected and that data are properly secured
- 7) There are gaps in the institutional and regulatory framework.
- 8) There is a lack of practical capacity to manage and preserve digital record
- 9) There are legal barriers
- 10) There are financial constraints

Through membership of CODATA, Kenya stands to find suitable good practices in Data Management and usage that can inform its decisions and save on wastage spent on duplication and loss of data. Kenya through membership in CODATA will benefit from international collaboration and knowledge sharing. Kenya hopes to access funding in collaboration with CODATA to address some of the challenges it faces.

JKUAT will establish an ICT Centre of Excellence and Open Data (iCEOD) with the mission to emerge as the premier research and development centre for technology transfer and open data for economic and human advancement. iCEOD will serve as a regional data sharing centre that will accelerate the generation, analysis, management and archiving of scientific data for the advancement of research and for development. iCEOD and CODATA Kenya will promote a culture of excellence and good practice in Open Data.